

ANNUAL REPORT

20
24

ABOUT ODISSEI

ODISSEI is the National Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences with diverse components, including access to data, expertise and computing, and offers a wide range of support opportunities. The infrastructure is a collaborative consortium of 45 member organisations, including social sciences faculties in the Netherlands, CBS, public research agencies, and research institutes. Its explicit aim is to unite the social sciences and create a common, national infrastructure for research.

We maintain and develop strategic partnerships with the leading academic and research institutions in the Netherlands, including [CBS](#), [DANS](#), [eScience Center](#), [SURF](#), and [Centerdata](#).

Through these partnerships, we provide access to the ODISSEI core facilities. ODISSEI also collaborates with [CLARIAH](#) (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) to support various intersecting developments across the Social Science and Humanities domain.

ODISSEI was launched in 2016 and the coordination is hosted by the Erasmus School of Social and Behavioral Sciences. All ODISSEI member organisations contribute to the operational budget of ODISSEI and ensure its financial sustainability and the continuity of services. Strategic development of new facilities is financed by external grants, especially NWO's Large Scale Research Infrastructure grants. In the past, ODISSEI secured financing of over €25m through Roadmap and SSHOC-NL grants, which were awarded in this scheme.

Internationally, ODISSEI is involved in [ERICs](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortia), which include [SHARE](#) (the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe) and the [European Social Survey](#). It is the current host of the [IPDLN](#) (the International Population Data Linkage Network, a worldwide network of researchers interested in data linkage).

ODISSEI IN NUMBERS

61,000

Interviews conducted by ODISSEI Surveys

15

Projects using the ODISSEI Secure Super
Computer

84

Summer School alumni

1,334

Publications

2,250,000

Minutes in the LISS panel provided for free
to researchers

1,602

Attendees at events

45

Members

4,156

Searches on the ODISSEI Portal
in the last 12 months

10,026

Datasets in the ODISSEI Portal

652

CBS Microdata Research Projects financed

MESSAGE FROM THE CHAIR

The last year has been one of both change and stability. Change, because the NWO Roadmap project ended and the SSHOC-NL project began; and because, after eight years of unrelenting service to digital infrastructure for the social sciences, our illustrious chair Pearl Dykstra has retired – handing over to myself. But there is also stability: ODISSEI is now clearly organized into thirteen distinct yet highly complementary tasks, transcending the specifics of any one project. These tasks, described in the present document, have made great strides in the past year and continue to do so. Personally, I am very excited to have started work on behalf of all researchers at our 45 member organizations to continue to improve social science and economics.

I would like to mention a few highlights of the past year. First, our community. The growing success of the ODISSEI conference continues to exhibit the growth of our broader community – as does the success of the ODISSEI SICSS summer school, and the impressive array of SoDa projects and Fellowships. I believe these and other activities show something important: ODISSEI is close to its users and experiences organic growth from the value it provides them. Going forward, maintaining and further expanding on our usage and recognition within the community will remain an important pillar of ODISSEI activities.

Second, ODISSEI has been building exciting new digital infrastructure. The new Trusted Upload and Linkage Procedure (TULP) now allows researchers to upload large datasets to the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) and, under safeguards, for the first time link them locally to CBS administrative registers. This opens up exciting new opportunities for research of the future. We have also seen SANE grow into its own, with several use cases now in practice, and much interest from external parties, which will form a basis for several potential collaborations going forward. SANE clearly fills an important gap in the digital infrastructure landscape. Similarly, the PORT data donation system has seen a growth in usage and development, allowing many new digital trace studies in conjunction with survey data from LISS and other studies.

Finally, a big scientific highlight this year was the PreFer data challenge, the first large-scale social science benchmarking study in the Netherlands. Not only did this study show the value of mass collaboration and benchmarking for scientific research, but it also motivated teams from across the world to develop highly innovative AI-based approaches to doing social science. We are looking forward to continuing these novel developments by welcoming these international teams back to the Netherlands during the Summer Incubator in 2025.

I encourage you to read through the many other highlights yourself. The fact that there are so many is a testament to ODISSEI's impressive scale and success. I look forward to continuing to bring this success to as many researchers as possible across the country, both at universities and at national knowledge institutes, so that we can meet ODISSEI's long standing ambition of : "better infrastructure, better evidence, better society".

DANIEL OBERSKI
CHAIR, ODISSEI

TABLE OF CONTENTS

01	Governance	7
02	Programme of work	6
03	Financial report	25
04	KPIs	29

GOVERNANCE

PAGES
7-8

GOVERNANCE

ODISSEI is the **Dutch National Infrastructure for Social Science** and provides access to a federated set of services to ODISSEI member organizations. Its explicit mission is to provide researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social inquiry.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as **innovative and diverse new forms of data**. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways.

ODISSEI now consists of **45 member organizations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI. As part of ODISSEI's new plan of work, 35 member organisations have already committed to ODISSEI membership until 2031.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of seven members: Claes de Vreese (DSW, chair), Susan Branje (DSW), Maarten van Ham (DSW), Viola Angelini (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Beate Völker (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Paulette Flore (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** consists of eleven members: Daniel Oberski (UU, Chair), Daniel Oberski (UU, Chair-elect), Tom Emery (EUR, Exec. Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU), Jessica Piotrowski (UvA), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ran van den Boom (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Collete Bos (NLeSC), and Anja Smit (DANS). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

The **Coordination Team** is composed of Tom Emery (Exec. Director), Lucas van der Meer (Chief Technical Officer), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Theodora Canciu (Project Manager), Evgeniia Krichever (Communications Manager) and Angelica Maineri (Data Manager).

An **International Advisory Board** has been established, including Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch (CESSDA), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University).

PROGRAMME OF WORK

PAGES
9-21

1

DATA FACILITY

1.1

CBS Microdata Access

1.2

ODISSEI Portal

1.3

ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

1.4

Secure Analysis Environment
(SANE)

The Data Facility supports access, linkage, and analysis of sensitive data in a safe, secure, and ethical manner.

The Data Facility workstream delivers improved data access, secure computing, and technical innovation. In 2024, this included major steps such as expanding dataset availability, improving metadata search and linkage through the Portal, developing the Secure Supercomputer and SANE environments, and deepening collaborations with key partners like CBS and SURF—all to support high-quality, responsible, and reproducible research.

Key Achievements

In 2024, ODISSEI significantly advanced its mission to strengthen the Dutch social science data infrastructure through enhanced data access, innovative tooling, and secure computing environments.

Central to ODISSEI’s work is the collaboration with CBS which cost **€624,000** in 2024. ODISSEI continues to lower the barriers to using the CBS microdata. 15 CBS microdata projects were financed through two rounds of the Microdata Access Grant (MAG), to support early career researchers and innovative research.

A key development in 2024 was the launch of the **CBS Data Storage** facility for large project files, which not only reduces storage costs for large CBS projects, but also promotes data reuse and research efficiency. At present, six large datasets are already available through the CBS Data Storage with many more in preparation.

These efforts are tightly integrated with the ODISSEI Portal, a comprehensive gateway to over 10,000 datasets from major Dutch data providers. In 2024 the Consortium for Individual Development (CID) metadata catalogue was also added to the ODISSEI Portal.

The Portal supports semantic search, enhances metadata through multilingual vocabularies, and enables advanced linkage opportunities. These facilitate more complex and innovative research and hardwire the FAIR principles into the ODISSEI infrastructure. An extensive document outlining the Portal’s design choices, insight into its main functionalities, information about the available metadata fields and their provenance for each Metadata Provider was also published.

Alongside the Portal, the ODISSEI Code Library, aggregates reusable analysis scripts from CBS and LISS data projects to encourage reproducibility and methodological transparency. Similarly, a proof of concept of the ODISSEI Knowledge Graph has been created, which unlocks access to research, data, and software for computational social science projects by modelling the Dutch social science academic ecosystem. The development of the Portal, the Code library, and Knowledge Graph cost €481,000 in 2024.

In 2024, ODISSEI expanded secure and scalable computing resources through the **ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC)**, which cost **€254,000**. The OSSC enables researchers to run high-performance analyses on sensitive data while complying with strict legal and security standards, with 15 active projects last year.

New features developed in 2024—such as a graphical App Dashboard—will soon be launched to lower the barrier to entry and make these powerful computing tools more accessible to non-technical users. Additionally, the Trusted Upload and Linkage Procedure (TULP) was finalised, allowing researchers to upload very large datasets to the OSSC with additional safeguards for sharing sensitive data with CBS. This has huge potential, especially in linking health science cohorts to administrative data.

For controlled access to sensitive datasets from providers other than CBS, the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE) was delivered in a production-ready version and cost €834,000 in 2024. SANE has been adopted by a growing number of data providers. SANE allows data holders to retain control over their datasets while enabling researchers to conduct analysis in a secure container. It has been integrated with the SURF and SSHOC-NL ecosystems,

Currently, agreements have been made with eight data providers to make sensitive data available within SANE, while three data providers are finalising the contracts to use SANE, and the number of users growing rapidly.

Across all tasks in the Data Facility stream, cross-cutting themes emerge: improved user access, promotion of data reuse, technical innovation, and close collaboration between institutions such as CBS, SURF, DANS, and universities. Together, these developments represent a cohesive and forward-looking investment in the infrastructure needed for cutting-edge, responsible, and collaborative social science research.

How to Request Data & Set Up SANE

If the researcher wants ODISSEI assistance in brokering with the prospective provider, the following steps are taken. The simple process to set up SANE without ODISSEI involvement is described on the [SURF servicedesk](#) page.

Step 1: Submit Your Data Access Request

Step 2: Approval Process

Step 3: SANE Environment Setup

Step 4: Free Access & Continued Use

[Request access](#)

2

OBSERVATORY

2.1

Data Collection Committee

2.2

LISS panel

2.3

Media Content Analysis Lab

The Observatory sustains and optimises valuable, long-standing data collections and the integration of new types of data.

The Observatory workstream strengthens the Dutch social science research ecosystem through sustained investment in high-quality data collection, panel studies, and digital media infrastructure. In 2024, ODISSEI secured Dutch participation in key international surveys, sustained the LISS panel, and advanced media content research through the Media Content Analysis Lab. These efforts, guided by FAIR principles and methodological transparency, ensure that Dutch researchers are equipped with robust, comparable, and ethically sourced data for both foundational and innovative research.

Key Achievements

With a dedicated budget of **€599,000** for data collection, ODISSEI secured long-term Dutch participation in essential international data initiatives. This included the completion of SHARE wave 10, resulting in 1,815 completed interviews. **SHARE** has been running in the Netherlands since 2004 and the 10th Wave ensures that we now have 20 years of data following individuals over 50.

ODISSEI also supported the participation of the Netherlands in the **International Social Survey Programme** after a 7 year hiatus. This included questions on the Digital Society and will be released along with data from 45 countries in early 2026.

ODISSEI also supported the operations of the **European Social Survey** and its preparations for Round 12 which will be completed in 2025. This is the first time in which the European Social Survey has been conducted in multiple modes and the team at Tilburg is therefore extending additional efforts in its preparations.

ODISSEI also sustained the Dutch participation in the **Luxembourg Income Study**. The Luxembourg Income and Wealth Studies provide access to a large amount of harmonized data on income and assets that are accessible via secure remote access environments. In 2024 LIS celebrated its 25th anniversary with a celebration hosted in Luxembourg.

In 2024, the **European Value Study** and the Dutch Parliamentary Election Study were not operated in 2024, but were still coordinated and supported through ODISSEI. Data from the 2023 **Dutch Parliamentary Election Study** were made available via the DANS SSH Data Station and indexed in the ODISSEI Portal alongside a data donation study conducted with PORT and capturing TikTok and YouTube watching habits during the election campaign.

The many efforts to support data collections in the Netherlands were bolstered by financial support from NWO and aligned with the SSHOC-NL initiative, making future data collection more stable and sustainable.

At the national level, the **LISS panel** remains a cornerstone of Dutch social science, supported by a **€758,000** budget in 2024. This covers the cost of maintaining the core operational costs of the panel and ensuring that it remains open and available to the Dutch Research Community. In 2024 this included a booster sample to ensure the continued representivity of the sample. As a result of the financing provided by ODISSEI, all members receive a 20% discount on fielding experiments in the LISS Panel. The panel sees wide uptake across disciplines, serving thousands of active users.

ODISSEI also facilitates access through free panel time via competitive grants that foster innovative, policy-relevant research. In 2024, nine projects were financed via the LISS Panel Grant. The panel also contributes data to several of the aforementioned international surveys, reinforcing ODISSEI's role in bridging national and international research infrastructure. LISS data was also recently central to the PreFer data challenge, which showcased interdisciplinary collaboration and the use of machine learning in demography.

Finally, the LISS Panel is central to the development of several new data collection tools including Mass Online Experiments and the PORT data donation software. LISS data is also linkable at the individual level with administrative microdata at CBS.

The **Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL)** addresses a critical infrastructure gap by enabling GDPR- and copyright-compliant analysis of media content. Backed by **€81,000** in funding in 2024, MCAL has built on existing Dutch tools to develop a user-friendly research environment, a linked open data inventory (MCALentory), and a platform for navigating the data landscape in Media Content Analysis in the Netherlands.

The initiative not only maps the media analysis landscape in the Netherlands but also lays the foundation for a national Media Corpus, which forms a central component of the Macroscopic proposal which is currently under evaluation by NWO and for which a result will be known in the summer of 2025. The Media Content Analysis Lab is proving vital in supporting the interoperability of Media Content Data with the wider ODISSEI data infrastructure and structured forms of data from surveys and administrative sources.

Across these tasks, ODISSEI's Observatory is unified by a commitment to FAIR data principles, methodological transparency, and support for both foundational and emerging research needs.

3

LABORATORY

3.1

Port

3.2

Mass Online Experiments

3.3

Disclosure Risk in Networks

The Laboratory opens up new avenues of scientific inquiry by exploiting innovative digital technologies.

The Laboratory workstream drives innovation in responsible, data-intensive research by developing secure, modular tools and infrastructure tailored to the social sciences. In 2024, ODISSEI advanced projects like Port for GDPR-compliant digital trace data collection, the Mass Online Experiment Lab for scalable network experiments, and POPNET for secure access to population-scale social network data. Through support for initiatives like the PreFer data challenge, the Laboratory also promotes benchmarking and methodological transparency. These developments reflect a strategic vision for ethical, scalable, and collaborative digital research.

Key Achievements

In 2024, the ODISSEI Laboratory laid critical groundwork for the future of responsible, data-intensive research in the social sciences by pioneering tools and infrastructure that enhance secure access, experimental scalability, and methodological innovation.

One standout development is **Port**, a GDPR-compliant software that enables citizens to donate digital trace data—such as WhatsApp records or bank statements—for scientific research while maintaining strict privacy safeguards. With a budget of **€20,000**, Port supported local data extraction, allowing participant oversight, and is already powering over 20 projects, with plans for broader interoperability across secure environments like SANE and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. This budget in 2024 was low as the work within SSHOC-NL was only just initiated, but this work will scale considerably in 2025-2028, building off the success of the D3I PDI-SSH project.

In parallel, the **Mass Online Experiment Lab (MoE)** tackles the challenge of conducting network-based experiments at population scale. Following successful pilots and supported by a budget of **€60,000** in 2024, new software developed under the OBELISS project now facilitates such experiments within the LISS panel using the oTree platform, allowing researchers to benefit from representative samples and deep background variables.

In 2025, Mass Online Experiments will be scaled up and fielded in the LISS Panel to support representative and large scale experiments in the social sciences for the first time. These experiments include hundreds of people participating in games simultaneously. This is a logistically challenging but highly powerful approach, allowing scientists to provide lab experimental settings at unprecedented scale.

This ecosystem-wide perspective is further strengthened by **POPNET**, a groundbreaking infrastructure for secure access to population-scale social network data. By developing novel methods for evaluating disclosure risks in highly complex datasets—especially those drawn from CBS administrative records—POPNET ensures that researchers can access rich network data without compromising privacy. The project is building a platform to automate risk assessments and plans to expand interoperability to other forms of sensitive data, including social media and historical sources.

Across all tasks, the ODISSEI Laboratory reflects a broader strategic vision: building modular, secure, and ethically sound tools that can be flexibly combined across projects. Through close collaborations with organisations such as Centerdata, Eyra, CBS, Utrecht University, and University of Groningen, the Laboratory is creating a scalable infrastructure for the next generation of digital social research.

Figure 1: Port Software: Step-by-step illustration of the workflow that allows for a privacy-preserving analysis of data download package

4

HUB

4.1

Coordination

4.2

Education

4.3

Support

The Hub creates a community of infrastructure users and offers the necessary support for the complex modelling of social phenomena.

The Hub workstream strengthens the foundation of ODISSEI by integrating project coordination, researcher support, and advanced training into a cohesive, future-ready infrastructure for the social sciences and humanities. Through high-impact events, governance structures, and communication channels, it ensures strategic alignment and broad community engagement. The workstream also drives capacity-building via the ODISSEI Summer School, workshops, and hands-on training, while providing tailored support through the SoDa team, the ELSI Helpdesk, and the FAIR Expertise Hub—empowering researchers to conduct ethical, high-quality, and innovative research.

Key Achievements

The *Hub* workstream aims to build a cohesive and future-proof infrastructure for social sciences and humanities in the Netherlands by supporting researchers, delivering advanced training, and ensuring robust project coordination.

Coordination efforts—supported by a budget of **€708,000** - ensure seamless management of ODISSEI activities, including grants administration, the coordination of SSHOC-NL, researcher support, and community engagement. The primary costs are the Coordination Team based at EUR as well the organization of events and coordination costs associated with the two LSRI projects operated during this time. These efforts are facilitated through high-quality communications, such as monthly newsletters and social media updates, as well as the organisation of key events (workshops, lectures, webinars, and symposiums).

A central pillar for ODISSEI is the ODISSEI Annual Conference, which in 2024 hosted over 440 participants and 120 presentations, reflecting the broad engagement across the social sciences in the Netherlands.

To further enhance governance, regular meetings such as **Project Insights**, **Steering Board**, and **Project Board meetings** have been organised, ensuring alignment across all activities. A shared Google Drive and dedicated Slack channel support transparency and real-time collaboration, and short “task plan” videos are being developed for wider outreach in 2025.

ODISSEI's educational programme, backed by **€159,000** in funding, has evolved to meet the growing demand for training in using its infrastructure for cutting-edge research. It started with hands-on workshops and has expanded into an advanced curriculum, with the **ODISSEI Summer School** (held in 2022, 2023, and 2024) providing intensive, two-week training for early-career researchers. The programme has received high demand, leading to plans to scale it up and explore further expansion in 2025.

In addition to the summer school, various workshops and tutorials are organised by the SoDa team.

These include topics such as microdata analysis, supercomputing for social scientists, and advanced data science methods. Interdisciplinary educational initiatives also continue, with workshops focused on open research tools and data analysis techniques being held across multiple domains.

Additionally, the Coordination Team has provided Q&A sessions for the Microdata Access Grant and LISS panel grant programmes.

Moreover, ODISSEI advanced benchmarking through the **PreFer data challenge**, a unique initiative to assess the predictability of fertility outcomes using LISS panel and CBS microdata.

This first-of-its-kind challenge in demography attracted 34 international interdisciplinary teams and exemplified how controlled competition can generate robust, reproducible insights in the social sciences.

ODISSEI's **SoDa team**, based at Utrecht University, offers ongoing support for methodological and technical challenges faced by researchers.

This includes the popular SoDa Fellowship Programme, where fellows receive direct mentorship and training in advanced data science techniques.

The **ODISSEI eScience team** provided ad-hoc support for strategic projects, such as the deployment of large-scale models and privacy-preserving technologies in research.

The **Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) Helpdesk**, developed as part of the support infrastructure, offers valuable assistance to researchers navigating complex ethical and legal considerations in their projects, and the **FAIR Expertise Hub** supports data communities in making their data more FAIR. Both can be accessed via the ODISSEI website.

FAIR. Together, these support initiatives reported a total of **€750,000** in spending.

RESEARCHER SPOTLIGHT

PAGES
21-23

”
The program provided an excellent opportunity to learn about innovative topics in computational social sciences, such as machine learning and network analysis while connecting with a diverse group of fellow junior social scientists. The combination of practical workshops, guest presentations from prominent scholars, and social activities made for an enjoyable experience.

Henry Abbink, Maastricht School of Business and Economics

My SoDa fellowship has been invaluable in addressing a key gap in my field—quantifying historical disease outbreaks. Nineteenth-century Dutch newspapers contain crucial data, but this source has never been turned into a reliable quantitative indicator. The SoDa team provided the computational tools and support needed to make this idea a reality.

Kristina Thomson, Wageningen University

”
In our project, we estimate the causal effect of daycare on children’s mental health and schooling outcomes in the Netherlands, applying complex simulations. At the CBS server, we could only perform the simulation for a small subsample. The OSSC allows us to conduct the simulation for the entire sample within a reasonable period.

Bettina Siflinger, Tilburg University

Research results: Implementation Barriers and Program Effectiveness: A Quasi-Experimental Study on an Extended School Week

This study investigated the impact of an extended school week on track recommendations, a key academic outcome used to guide students' secondary school placement, across 30 primary schools. The intervention was part of a larger urban policy initiative implemented in one of the most socioeconomically disadvantaged regions in the Netherlands, aiming to improve educational opportunities for children in underserved communities.

Using comprehensive CBS register data spanning from 2010 to 2020, the researcher examined whether the intervention led to structural changes in track recommendations at the school level. To establish a comparison group, control schools were selected through matching based on a range of educational and demographic variables. The findings show that the intervention did not lead to a consistent or significant increase in track recommendations compared to the matched control schools. Potential factors that may explain these null results include barriers to effective implementation, such as the top-down nature of the policy design, inconsistent program quality and coordination across schools, and persistent teacher shortages.

Custers, G. (2025). Implementation Barriers and Program Effectiveness: A Quasi-Experimental Study on an Extended School Week. *Educational Policy*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/08959048241309345>

Research results: Large Language Model (LLM) Driven Text-Mining to Understand and Support Students' SRL Processes

Research has shown that self-regulated learning (SRL) skills are a strong predictor of academic success, particularly in digital learning environments. However, many students struggle with self-regulation and could benefit from targeted SRL training and support tools. A recent intervention using a text-based conversational agent (CA) to support students' SRL activities yielded promising results. At the same time, it revealed that students engage with the CA differently depending on their SRL skill levels. This underscores the need for personalized support—ensuring that students with low SRL skills receive adequate guidance, while those with high SRL skills are not over-supported.

To better understand how students with varying SRL levels interact with the CA—and to tailor support more effectively—this project uses a large language model (LLM)-assisted text mining. The goal is to analyze data from a previous study through sentiment analysis, thematic analysis, and the development of a text classifier capable of identifying and scoring indicators of specific SRL processes in student interactions. For this purpose, OpenAI's ChatGPT models are used to conduct the text-mining analyses.

Researcher: Gabrielle Martins van Jaarsveld.

FINANCIAL OVERVIEW

PAGES
24-26

FINANCIAL REPORTING 2024

The ODISSEI budget has become increasingly complex due to the multitude of projects it is engaged in. With this in mind and as we move to a new reporting schedule for the financial results, financial reporting will be rationalized and simplified in three ways.

First, because activities executed by ODISSEI are increasingly complex, all expenditures will be classified under one of 13 tasks. These tasks loosely match the original tasks as set out in the ODISSEI Roadmap project and are relatively homogenous in terms of their activities and executing parties. All the tasks in the Roadmap, SSHOC-NL, PDI-SSH, and Macroscope can be mapped onto these 13 ODISSEI Tasks. In addition, we will also report costs incurred by partner organizations within projects ODISSEI participates but for specific tasks where ODISSEI is not active (e.g. Task 2.3 in SSHOC-NL). The mapping of these tasks across all projects is provided in Table 1 below. This prevents the reporting of multiple individual project budgets, and instead allows an overview of how all projects contribute to a singular coherent work programme as represented in this report.

Second, revenues are divided into earmarked and non-earmarked revenues. Earmarked revenues primarily stem from grants and awarded to ODISSEI for a specific task or action. Unearmarked revenues are general contributions or revenues which are not specific and maybe allocated at the discretion of the ODISSEI boards. Unearmarked revenues are primarily membership fees which have not been pre-allocated as matching for a specific funding application as well as international membership rebates made by NWO. Coordination Team will report the annual unearmarked revenue, the amount that has subsequently been allocated, and the amount that remains unallocated. This allows the boards to see the ongoing cash reserve of ODISSEI. For 2024, there were €887,000 unearmarked revenues which were exclusively from rebates on international memberships. These remained unallocated and so provide a cash reserve moving into 2025.

Third, all revenues will be delineated into 'ongoing' and 'structural'. Ongoing revenues refer to projects that are time constrained and cannot in themselves be considered sustainable. Structural funding is that which is designed to be perpetual, even if it is to be reviewed later. Whilst there is a strong overlap between Ongoing and Earmarked funds on the one hand and Structural and Unearmarked funds on the other, these are not always like for like. For example membership revenues which have been used as matching in funding proposals are then structural and allocated. To support the evaluation of the sustainability of the infrastructure, the percentage of revenues which are structural and ongoing are reported.

The financial results for 2024 (Table 2) show that ODISSEI spent €5,5 million across the 13 tasks. Of this, €198k was spent in tasks exclusively associated with CLARIAH. Tasks that were reinitiated as part of the SSHOC-NL project such as Popnet, PORT, and Mass Online Experiments, reported low costs due to the initiation process. These costs will climb in the coming years to reflect deferred spending from year 1 of SSHOC-NL. Coordination costs were 13% of the overall budget of the infrastructure. Unearmarked revenue was €887,000 which exclusively refers to the contribution of NWO to international membership fees for the period 2023-2024 for which ODISSEI had previously met the costs. Due to these international fee's, the proportion of revenue that was structural was 25.38%.

Table 1 – Mapping of Tasks in ODISSEI

#	ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	ODISSEI 2020 Tasks	SSHOC-NL Tasks	Macroscope	Other Projects
1.1	CBS	Data Facility	1.1	1.3	1.3	
1.2	Portal	Data Facility	1.4; 3.1; 3.2	4.1; 4.2; 4.3	1.1	CD2
1.3	OSSC	Data Facility	1.3; 2.4		1.2	
1.4	SANE	Data Facility		1.1		SANE, FBB
2.1	Data Collection	Observatory	2.1; 2.3	2.2	2.1	SHARE, ESS
2.2	Online Panels	Observatory	3.3	2.1	2.2	PANL
2.3	MCAL	Observatory	2.2		2.3, 3.2	
3.1	PORT	Laboratory		1.2	3.3	D3I
3.2	Mass Online Experiments	Laboratory		3.3		
3.3	PopNet	Laboratory		3.2		Popnet
4.1	Coordination	Hub	4.1	5.3	4.1	SBD, PDI-SSH
4.2	Education	Hub	4.2; 4.5	5.2	4.3	
4.3	Support	Hub	4.3; 4.4	5.1	4.2	FIP, MUW, FAIR
CLARIAH				2.3; 3.1	3.1	

CD2 = Child Development Data Portal Work; SANE = Secure Analytical Environment [PDI-SSH]; FBB = Firmbackbone [PDI-SSH]; SHARE = Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe [NWO – International]; ESS = European Social Survey [NWO-International]; PANL = Dutch Participant Platform [PDI-SSH]; D3I = Digital Data Donation Infrastructure [PDI-SSH]; Popnet = Population Network Analysis [PDI-SSH]; SBD = SoBigData Europe [Horizon Europe]; PDI-SSH = PDI-SSH Coordination [OCW]; FIP = FAIR Implementation Platform [PDI-SSH]; MUW = Meer Uren Werkt [Groeifonds]; FAIR = Untangling FAIR [TDCC]

Table 2 – ODISSEI Expenditures & Revenues for 2024

ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	2024
CBS	Data Facility	624
Portal	Data Facility	481
OSSC	Data Facility	254
SANE	Data Facility	834
Data Collection	Observatory	599
Online Panels	Observatory	758
MCAL	Observatory	81
PORT	Laboratory	20
Mass Online Experiments	Laboratory	60
PopNet	Laboratory	0
Coordination	Hub	708
Education	Hub	159
Support	Hub	750
CLARIAH		198
Total		5525
Revenues		
Unearmarked Revenues		887
Unearmarked and Allocated Revenues		0
Remaining Unallocated Revenues		887
Cumulative Unallocated Revenues		887
Structural Funding		1627
Ongoing Funding		4784
Structural Funding as %		25.38%

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

PAGES
27-29

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year, the current status of each KPI is reported and new targets are established. The KPIs are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regard to the specific and concrete aims of the project. Overall, ODISSEI has been very successful in achieving its KPIs over the past 5 years as reflected by the high number of met targets in the table below. As of 2026 the KPIs will be refreshed as ODISSEI moves into a new phase of development.

Table 3 – Key Performance Indicators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target</i>	<i>Current</i>
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and 9 economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties and 11 Economics faculties are members.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	ODISSEI is now a partner in SoBigData Europe and TWIN4DEM, collaborates with EOSC-ENTRUST.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE by 2024	ODISSEI White Paper has been published and ODISSEI is host of IPDLN 2026.
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 11% of all researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 3% of all researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	50 unique visitors per month by 2025	On average, 360 unique visitors per month in 2024.
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year for 2022, 2023 and 2024	17 active in 2024
Number of projects spanning more than 2 facilities	5 per year by 2025	19 projects in 2024
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	SSHOC-NL project awarded and Macroscopic project submitted
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	80% of partners have committed until 2031 conditional on Macroscopic award

Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	1,500 by May 2025
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	15 projects completed before end of 2024	28 projects acquired up to October 2024
Science & Technology		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	3 per year by 2025	5 up to 2024
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2025	22 in 2024
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2025	178 in 2024
Social and Economic Impact		
Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organisations	Five datasets from non-academic organisations accessible by 2025	10
Number of government agencies participating as member organisations	7 by 2025	6
Number of website visits	50,000 per year by 2025	36,000 by May 2025
Mentions in key policy documents	3 per year	5 in 2024
Press mentions of ODISSEI related research in the Netherlands	10 per year	Monitoring as of 2025
Communication		
Number of social media (e.g. X(Twitter), LinkedIn) subscribers	2,500 by 2025	2,290 by May 2025
Number of newsletter subscribers	Total of 1,000 by 2025	1,491 by May 2025
Attracting New Talent		
Number of international scientists recruited by ODISSEI	20 by the end of 2024	18 in 2024
Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc)	5 per year	9 in 2024
Retention of coordination staff	80% retention year on year	100%

PHOTO CREDITS

Page 15: Photo by Austin Distel on [Unsplash](#)

Page 24: Photo by Scott Graham on [Unsplash](#)

www.odissei-data.nl